

The Impact Of The Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies.

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Abstract: Purpose: To demonstrate the impact of Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies

Methodology: The study employs a descriptive and quantitative methodology. As a means to collect data, managers got self-administered questionnaires, which produced a sample of 82 respondents. Descriptive and correlational methods were applied for data analysis.

Results: There is a statistically significant effect at a significant level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) Of the Leadership Style Dimensions (transformational leadership style, nal leadership style laissez-faire leadership style) On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Transactional leadership, Laissez-faire leadership

Introduction

Based on the resources that they produce or use, industries in the US are categorized into three main economic groups. Raw materials are extracted or gathered in the primary sector. Finished goods are produced in the secondary, or manufacturing, sector. The service sector, which is arguably the largest of the three, makes up the third category. The service sector, additionally referred to as the tertiary sector, differs from the other economic sectors in that it produces intangible goods.

There is no material extraction or growth in the service industry. Rather, the service sector is wide and includes businesses that provide services to clients. These services, which support the other two industries and are frequently final, could include transportation, consulting, and training. Services like construction, healthcare, maintenance, repair, administration, and gastronomy can also be produced in the tertiary sector; these are less closely associated with resource extraction and manufacturing.

In 2021, the services sector made up approximately 77.6 percent of the US GDP. The professional, scientific, and technical services sector has emerged as the most prominent one within the service industry in recent times. With an estimated 1.84 trillion dollars added to the GDP in 2021, the industry has made the largest recent economic contribution to the United States. The food services and beverage industry made up 524 billion dollars of the GDP in that same year. Still up for debate, though, is which industries should be factored into this calculation. Certain industries appear to change their sector classification from one organization to another. As an illustration, the construction industry is classified as a production industry by the US Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA). It is included in their reports along with the industries that produce goods, and its value to the GDP is added to that of the manufacturing sector. On the other hand, the Institute for Supply Management (ISM) views the building industry as a component of the services industry. The construction sector contributed approximately 4.2% of the country's GDP in 2021. For a detailed analysis of the service industry in the US, consult the Services Purchasing Manager's Index (PMI). Based on a survey sent to over 400 companies across 19 primary industries, the PMI is calculated based on each company's overall GDP contribution. Every PMI is made up of a collection of economic sector indices that are meant to gauge the overall health of that sector. These indices for the service industry are supplier deliveries, employment, business activity, and new orders. The overall percentage of the sector's PMI reflects their performance. A positive state of affairs is indicated by an index value above 50%, whereas a negative value indicates economic decline. As an illustration, the employment PMI for the service sector, which had a value of 49.8 in December 2022, indicates that employment in the sector was declining at the end of the year. All things considered, the advancement of contemporary technology has spurred the expansion of the service industry, raising its overall value. The number of job opportunities in the service industries has significantly increased as a by product of the sector's expansion. It is anticipated that there will be 6.1 million workers in the transportation and warehousing sector alone by 2026, up from 5.98 million in 2019. The service sector contributes to the growth of the American economy in more ways than just creating jobs. Services are still in high demand for import and export, even though the service sector generates intangible services. The value of services exported from the

United States has been rising recently. At 81.05 billion US dollars in November 2022, it was worth almost 10 billion more than the same month the year before. Financial services accounted for nearly 14 billion US dollars of the services exported in that month. According to Statista Research Department data released on December 19, 2023, the value of imported services into the US was estimated to be around 58.51 billion USD that same month. Industry-specific value added to the US gross domestic product in 2023 (measured in US dollars)

Organizational leadership has changed as a result of the 21st century's shifting circumstances. The traits and actions that surface have an impact on the relationship quality of the leader. According to Ivan and Terra (2017), a leader's role in organizational dynamics is crucial because they act as a watchdog over societal changes and use that information to take both intra- and inter-organizational actions. According to Albloshi and Nawar (2015), the increasingly dynamic global market has led to research on and interest in leadership in recent decades. Organizations are interested in this topic, according to Silva, Paschoalotto, and Endo (2020), because it is thought to offer managers a chance to challenge conventional wisdom and improve the quality of work for both themselves and their teams. Wegner, Tontini, Costa, Muller Junior, and Silva (2021) in this regard.

An environment of ideas that is conducive to innovation can be fostered through leadership that involves dialogue and conversations involving a range of opinions. A deeper comprehension of social dynamics and group accomplishments can be attained by examining their styles (Lunardi, Degenhart & Zonatto, 2019; Soardo, Fanton & Júnior, 2020; Lucatelli, Tormen-Ferreira, Alberton & Marinho, 2021). In light of the previously mentioned, the current study aims to respond to the following research question: How do managers of micro and small and beachwear businesses in Tampa, Florida, execute leadership roles that are related to organizational culture? As a result, the main goal was decided upon to assess the connection between organizational culture and the management style employed by managers of micro and small underwear and beachwear businesses in Tampa/CW.

Organizational studies find relevance in studying and comprehending organizational culture because they help to clarify various outcomes at the individual and organizational levels (Giorgi, Lockwood, & Glynn, 2015; Machado, Maranhão & Pereira, 2016). In response, Paz, Fernandes, Carneiro, and Melo (2020) view organizational culture as a system that needs to be taken into account when putting policies, guidelines, and actions into place that benefit the employee, who is then dedicated to the accomplishment of objectives, the survival, and expansion of the organization.

Research objective

Main objective: To demonstrate the impact of Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies

The following sub-goals branch out from this goal:

To demonstrate the impact of transformational leadership style on the manager's manifest.

To demonstrate the impact of transactional leadership style on the manager's manifest.

To demonstrate the impact of laissez-faire leadership style on the manager's manifest.

Study questions

Main questions what is the impact of Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies?

From this question, the following sub-questions emerge

what is the impact of transformational leadership style on the manager's manifest?

What is the impact of transactional leadership style on the manager's manifest?

what is the impact of laissez-faire leadership style on the manager's manifest?

2.2 Leadership

The definition of leadership is constantly changing, it is challenging to pin down exactly what it means (Day & Harrison, 2007). It varies based on the methodology used, the area of interest of the researchers, the viewpoints of the individual researchers, and their line of inquiry (Campos, Araújo, Moraes, & Kilimnik 2013). As previously noted by Crozatti (1998), a professional who manages these teams and is in line with the company's values, vision, and mission is essential for the team and employees to complete their tasks on schedule and with greater quality. According to Yukl (2010), the definition of leadership encompasses behavior, influence, interaction patterns, relationship roles, and holding an administrative position. The following are some representative definitions from the past 50 years: There are three main ways to apply this: a) to gain more control over a mechanical submission following the company's regular guidelines; b) to influence the actions of an organized group to achieve a goal; and c) to give the collective effort a purpose and incite the desire to put in more effort to reach the suggested goal.

According to Silva, Nunes, and Andrade (2019), the definitions of leadership styles are associated with the process by which an individual selects a style that best suits the needs of both the leader and the self in terms of both organization and individual needs. According to studies by Lunardi, Desenhard, and Zonatto (2019), these dynamic styles can direct and influence an individual's behavior to fit the situation, making them an important variable in the organizational context. To solve potential issues that may arise in the organization, a leader using the transformational leadership style encourages his subordinates to be imaginative and, in some situations, inventive. This pertains to the process of influence that leaders possess, which results in the dedication of those under their guidance and cultivates their capacity to surpass personal boundaries in support of the organization's or group's objectives. (2009, Bergamini). In the workplace, people with transformational leadership styles ought to be supported (Rezende, Carvalho Neto & Tanure, 2014).

According to Burns (1978), transactional leadership is defined as a relationship of surface-level ties based on an exchange of interests centered on personal goals, whereas transformational leadership deeply inspires followers to give their all to accomplish organizational goals and builds a relationship of trust between those involved.

Laissez-faire leadership, which is also referred to as liberal, is characterized by leaders who delegate authority to their followers, refuse to make decisions, and only intervene when a more significant issue emerges to achieve their goals. If this is not the case, the lack of responsibility is evident in this style, according to Bass and Bass (1993). Escandon-Barbosa and Hurtado-Ayala (2016) clarify that, in contrast to transactional and transformational leadership, this style makes it impossible to find a work environment with clearly defined objectives because the person in charge does not take responsibility for any action plan and delays making decisions, thereby ignoring their responsibilities.

Study, Kumar and Upadhaya In 2020 investigated the role that organizational culture plays as a mediator in the relationship between work-family enrichment and servant leadership. In northern India, data was gathered from 223 teachers. The outcomes validated organizational culture's mediating role. Paais and Pattiruhu (2020) looked into the impact of organizational culture, leadership, and motivation on job satisfaction among 155 employees of an Indonesian company. The findings indicated that while employee performance is influenced by 73.5% of the variables of motivation, leadership, culture, and job satisfaction, job satisfaction is influenced by 57.4% of the variables of motivation, leadership, and culture.

Madi Odeh, Obeidat, Jaradat, Masa´deh and Alshurideh (2021) studied the perception of 379 employees of Dubai service companies on the effect of transformational leadership style through the mediating effect of adaptive culture on organizational resilience. The study's findings confirmed that adaptive culture plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational resilience and that transformational leadership has a significant positive impact on both.

Types of Leadership Styles

By Zoe Ashbridge (2024).

In addition to helping you better understand your ideas, decision-making process, and potential strategies to employ when making business decisions, the leadership style also enables you to give employees the direction and feedback they need.

Additionally, you can gain insight into your direct reports' perceptions of you and the reasons behind their possible feedback. Employees may be telling you that you're an autocratic boss who needs to adjust your style if they feel suppressed at work and don't get many opportunities to voice their opinions.

For example, employees may tell you you're an autocratic boss who needs to change if they feel suppressed and don't get many chances to express their opinions.

Transformational leadership

Transformational leaders motivate team members, gain over their trust and confidence, and lead staff members toward achieving organizational objectives.

Additionally, transformational leadership always enhances the company's practices and motivates staff members to move forward and expand their abilities.

A transformational leader's ultimate objectives are to make a long-lasting good influence, inspire their team to reach their greatest potential, and drive the organization to success.

Transformational leadership: advantages and disadvantages

Pros:

- Puts a greater focus on the vision of the business
- Employees are usually more aligned with company values
- Build stronger relationships – resulting in higher employee engagement and retention

Cons:

- Constant pushing towards an ambitious goal can lead to employee burnout
- A high level of continuous motivation is required
- Transformational leaders can unintentionally cause too much

This Leadership Style Is Effective for Businesses

Innovative thinking can be promoted in a team by transformational leaders. Businesses can use this to improve their procedures and increase profitability and productivity. Additionally, it can support employee motivation, morale, and satisfaction.

This is a highly motivating style of leadership where staff members are supported and motivated to realize their potential. New employees under this kind of leadership may receive a list of objectives and due dates for achieving them. While the objectives may seem simple initially, managers will eventually allocate more work and difficult duties to staff members as they advance within the organization. "Instead of focusing on the objectives of the business, transformational leaders may overlook each person's unique learning curve. It's critical to collaborate with your team to update benchmarks because staff burnout can also become a problem.

Example of a Transformational leader

"Pam Bump is HubSpot's head of content innovation and research. Although she identifies with a few types of transformational leadership, it is the one she most firmly identifies with as her dominant style. Bump talks about her background as a transformative leader. Her responsibilities before becoming a manager included expanding her audience, developing her brand, trying new things, and entering new markets." "I've always jumped at big problem-solving opportunities, unclear requests from leadership, and figuring out risky investments for my businesses," the woman claims. "So, whether we're working on a group experiment or each member is looking into, starting, and growing their high-ROI project, I encourage my team to do the same." She is an inspiring leader who deliberately tries to strike a balance between the objectives of the company, the needs of the team, and the needs of the individual. It is a difficulty that transformational leaders sometimes overlook: the demands of everyone in the organization as well as the needs of individual learners. Bump has the answer: "I check in with my direct reports about their growth, what they're working on, and work that can help them grow their skills or visibility while also supporting team goals to balance ambitious overall, transformative team-wide goals and individual teammate needs." In addition to weekly one-on-ones, Bump hosts semi-regular career conversations where they talk about their individual long-term goals and the strategies or abilities they can employ to achieve them.

Transactional leadership

"Transactional leadership uses incentives and penalties to influence and guide behavior. These managers actively supervise the work of their staff members and establish clear guidelines and expectations. When an employee meets a goal, they inform them that rewards are on the way. However, if individuals aren't reaching their goals, they might need to do more 1:1s or check-ins. Established standards and goals must be met, and the status quo must be upheld, according

to this leadership style. It also presumes that teams are driven by rewards and require structure and supervision to achieve organizational objectives."

Transactional leadership: advantages and disadvantages

Pros:

- It's easy to understand and implement
- Employees know exactly what's expected of them
- The potential for rewards can be really motivating

Cons:

- Reduced employee innovation and creativity
- Punishments can result in high employee turnover
- The reliance on rules and procedures makes for a rigid work environment

Due to its focus on results, pre-existing structures, and established systems of incentives and penalties, this style is well-liked in industry businesses. Additionally, this leadership style honors and values commitment. Because they understand expectations, employees might feel more secure when transactional leaders provide clear and structured expectations. Employees are also aware of exactly what they will receive in exchange for achieving company objectives. This strategy focuses less on building relationships with employees, providing coaching, and building cooperation and more on utilizing rewards to motivate. If only some members of the different teams are reward-motivated, it might be difficult to keep them interested. This can result in low innovation and a fear of penalty."

Laissez-Faire Leadership

"You'll correctly believe that laissez-faire leadership is the least aggressive kind of leadership if you can recall your high school French. "Let them do" is how the French phrase "laissez-faire" is translated. Leaders who practice it delegate almost all authority to their staff and hardly speak up unless necessary. The following are some vital characteristics of laissez-faire leadership

- . Enough direction, advice, and feedback
- . Very little control and interference
- . High levels of independence and autonomy
- . Empowerment as well as trust

"Laissez-faire leaders make staff members responsible for their work. Many workers are motivated to perform at their highest level by this. A relaxed corporate culture is frequently created by this kind of boss. Because of this, it's a useful model for creative industries like product design or advertising companies. Additionally, it works well for companies with highly skilled employees." For example, the leader of a young startup may have a laissez-faire attitude and set no firm office rules about deadlines or work hours. While they concentrate on the general operations of managing the business, they may have total faith in their staff. It is this high degree of trust that makes workers under laissez-faire bosses feel important. They obtain the necessary information and then apply their resources and expertise to achieve their business objectives. "There are disadvantages to laissez-faire leadership, even while it might empower workers by allowing them to work however they see fit. It can hinder the growth of a team and present difficulties for unskilled or new hires who would need direction as they ramp up. In addition to creating a culture of working in silos where individuals may operate independently rather than as a cohesive team, roles and duties can also become ambiguous. Maintaining this leadership style under control is crucial since it might fail to see vital possibilities for learning and corporate progress.

Example of a Laissez-Faire Leader

"Meg Prater works at HubSpot as the senior manager of content. Prater characterizes her leadership style as a combination of coaching and laissez-faire."I like to customize my style to each person on my team to best fit their working styles and career goals," says Prater, "but I also like to trust the people I hire to do great work."Prater notes that while some members of her team do better under a stronger structure, others do better with more independence. Strong cooperation and communication are essential, whatever the team."Making sure my direct reports understand our team's and the company's overall goals, as well as how their output contributes to those goals, is my priority (and my job)," she says.

"Once our expectations are in line, we can work together to find projects that make a difference, all the while following our interests and promoting professional development within the team."A laissez-faire leader faces the difficulty of finding a balance between the need to provide inexperienced team members with the necessary direction and the desire to trust them. My senior manager in my early career was a laissez-faire leader, and I occasionally felt like I had no

direction. But as a fearless problem-solver, I also valued my independence under this kind of management. Though I can understand how that could be challenging for certain team members, in some ways, having to solve the challenge alone helped build those problem-solving abilities. Prater's appreciation of the leadership job and the advantages of providing feedback to staff members also influence her coaching leadership approach. Prater states, "Shortly after I became a manager, I had the pleasure of working with an amazing leadership coach." "Being a kind manager rather than a nice manager" is a concept that she implanted in me. Prater points out that to be kind, it might be easy to minimize criticism or demands. Although it feels less awkward, in the long run, neither the management nor the direct report always gains from it. In the end, difficult talks are the ones that foster growth on both sides, so it's important to be direct, unambiguous, and actionable. As a manager, that counsel has truly influenced me. Even though I'm not perfect at it.

Methods Theoretical:

Based on the exposed studies, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H01: There is no statistically significant impact at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) of the Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies

The following hypotheses branch out from this hypothesis:

H01.1: There is no statistically significant impact at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) of the transformational leadership style on the manager's manifest.

H01.2: There is no statistically significant impact at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) of the transactional leadership style on the manager's manifest.

H01.3: There is no statistically significant impact at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) of the laissez-faire leadership style on the manager's manifest.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out with a quantitative, descriptive, the purpose of the survey and cross-sectional approach was to assess the correlation between organizational culture and the leadership that managers of small and micro Underwear and beachwear businesses in Tampa, Florida, provide. The search universe included 96 beachwear and Underwear businesses in Tampa, Florida, connected to the Tampa/CW Commercial and Industrial Association, yielding a sample size of 82.

Two questionnaires made up the data collection tool. The purpose of the first section was to gauge managers' opinions of Leadership Style. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire by Bass and Avolio (2004) was the basis for the second section of the questionnaire, which asked participants to evaluate their The Manager's Manifest.

Google Forms was used to help structure the data collection tool digitally. Respondents can access the questionnaire by clicking on a link. First, a pre-test was conducted. To confirm whether the questionnaire was appropriate for the respondents, the link to it was forwarded to five managers from the Underwear and beachwear industries as well as two local professors.

Following the suggested modifications, on November 18, 2021, an email asking for the link to be added to the list of entrepreneurs connected to the Association was sent to the secretary of the Commercial and Industrial Association of Tampa. The secretary resent the email to all associates on November 30, 2021. Individual or private emails were sent using the contact details listed on the companies' websites to reach out to additional respondents. The form was closed on December 8, 2021, although all contacts had already been made. It was noted that responses to the form had stopped.

4.2 Cronbach Alpha Coefficient test

To ensure the reliability of the research tool, all values must be higher than (0.70). The following table shows the dimensions of the independent variable (Leadership Style)

Table (1): Internal consistency coefficient test

No	Dimensions	Alpha value
1	transformational leadership style	0.853
2	transactional leadership style	0.881
3	aissez-faire leadership style	0.861
Leadership Style		0.899
Manager's Manifest		0.919
Search tool		0.878

The values ranged between (0.852-0.881), and the value of the independent variable (Leadership Style) was (0.899), while the dependent variable (Manager's Manifest) was (0.919), and the alpha value of the research tool was (0.878), and therefore all values are greater than (0.70) This indicates the possibility of ensuring and trusting the research tool to conduct statistical analysis.

Multicollinearity test

This test clarifies the issue of correlation between variables, as if the value is greater than (0.80), this indicates that there is a problem in the correlation between variables.

Table (2): Correlation matrix for independent variables

Dimensions	transformational leadership style	transactional leadership style	aissez-faire leadership style
transformational leadership style	1.000		
transactional leadership style	0.669**	1.000	
aissez-faire leadership style	0.648**	0.551**	1.000

The correlation coefficient between the two variables (transformational leadership style) and (transactional leadership style) was (0.669), which is less than (0.80), and therefore there is no phenomenon of multi-linear correlation between the variables. The correlation coefficient between (transformational leadership style) and (aissez-faire leadership style) also appeared (0.648), and (transactional leadership style) and (aissez-faire leadership style) appeared (0.551), and therefore all values are less than (0.80). This is an indication of the absence of the problem of high multicollinearity (Guajarati, 2004). To confirm the previous result, the test was conducted. the next:

Table (3): Results of the test of the variance inflation factor and the permissible variance

Dimensions	VIF	Tolerance
transformational leadership style	1.901	0.526
transactional leadership style	2.010	0.498
aissez-faire leadership style	2.985	0.335

The results obtained from the multiple linear correlation analysis show that the variable (transformational leadership style) reached VIF (1.901) and Tolerance (0.526), while (transactional leadership style) reached VIF (2.010) and Tolerance (0.498), while the variable (aissez-faire leadership style) The VIF reached (2.985), and the Tolerance reached (0.335). This confirms that there is no problem with a multi-linear correlation between the variables, because the VIF values must fall between (1-10) while the Tolerance value must range between (0.1 -1) Which enhances the reliability of statistical analysis.

Description of research variables

Table 4: Arithmetic averages and materiality for dimensions of artificial intelligence

No	Dimensions	Arithmetic average	standard deviation	Rank	Materiality
1	transformational leadership style	3.782	0.313	3	high
2	transactional leadership style	3.949	0.300	1	high
3	aissez-faire leadership style	3.911	0.310	2	high
Leadership Style		3.880	0.301		high
Manager's Manifest		3.840	0.351		high

The overall average in terms of relative importance was high, as the overall average for the independent variable was (3.880), and the variable (transactional leadership style) took first place with an average of (3.949) with high relative importance, while the variable (laissez-faire leadership style) took second place with an average of (3.911). The relative importance is high, and the variable (transformational leadership style) takes last place with an average of (3.782) and also high relative importance. The follow-up variable (Manager's Manifest) received an average score of (3.840) and a high relative importance.

Hypothesis testing

Main research hypothesis H01: “There is no statistically significant Impact at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) Of the Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies.”

The table below shows the multiple regression analysis, and the results are as follows:

Table (5): * Results of testing the impact of “Leadership Style” on “Manager's Manifest”

Dependent variable	Model Summary		ANOVA			Coefficients				
	Correlation coefficient R	Coefficient of determination R ²	Calculated F value	Df	Sig F*	Independent variable	B	Standard error	Calculated T	Sig t*
Manager's Manifest	0.754	0.569	199.299	3	0.000	transformational leadership style	0.171	0.052	3.288	0.000
						transactional leadership style	0.421	0.061	6.902	0.000
						laissez-faire leadership style	0.248	0.041	6.049	0.000

*The effect is statistically significant at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The table above shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variable “Leadership Style” and the variable “Manager's Manifest”, as (56.9%) of the variance in “Manager's Manifest” can be explained by “Leadership Style” combined, as There is a significant impact of all applications of Leadership Style (transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, laissez-faire leadership style) On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies.

Therefore, we reject the main hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis:

“There is a statistically significant effect at a significant level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) Of the Leadership Style On The Manager's Manifest In Small Business Companies.”

To determine which of the dimensions (transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, laissez-faire leadership style) have the greatest impact on Manager's Manifest, a stepwise regression analysis was used, as follows:

Table (6): Results of stepwise regression analysis for the main hypothesis H01

Sample	AI	B	Calculated T	Sig* T	Coefficient of determination R ²	Calculated F	Sig* F
the first	transactional leadership style	0.394	5.149	0.000	0.509	298.639	0.000
the second	transactional leadership style	0.413	5.964	0.000	0.532	225.245	0.000
	laissez-faire leadership style	0.223	4.999	0.000			
the third	transactional leadership style	0.421	6.902	0.000	0.569	199.299	0.000
	laissez-faire leadership style	0.248	6.049	0.000			
	transformational leadership style	0.171	3.288	0.000			

*The effect is statistically significant at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The results of the stepwise regression analysis conducted during the research show the arrangement of the variables and their impact on Manager's Manifest based on Leadership Style. According to these results, the independent variables

and their impact on Manager's Manifest were arranged, with “transactional leadership style” taking first place, then “laissez-faire leadership style,” and finally “transformational leadership style.”

5. Conclusion

To reach the company's goals and objectives, a leader must be able to align their own goals and objectives with those of the organization and modify their style of leadership to suit the specific circumstances. This study's main goal was to assess the connection between Leadership Style and the Manager Manifest in companies of micro and small underwear and beachwear businesses in Tampa/CW.

It was discovered that managers viewed transactional leadership as the most prevalent style, followed by transformational. According to Burns (1978), transactional leadership is the process of completing tasks and activities with common goals that lead to the performance that the manager expects. It is based on an exchange relationship. Within the particular context of beachwear, knickers, and micro businesses in Ilhota, South Carolina, the manager's ability to lead a sector can be limited by the fact that they frequently have responsibilities that are at odds with their qualifications or experience. To achieve the desired outcome in this situation, the transactional leader cultivates reward-based behavior.

Different relationships between Leadership Style and the Manager Manifest In Small Business Companies were found when the conjectured hypotheses were tested, and The results showed that there is a relationship between Leadership Style and the Manager Manifest In Small Business Companies with all dimensions of the independent variable

In terms of constraints, it is important to highlight that the leadership style and the culture type originated from the opinions of the same respondents; this feature might have made it difficult to distinguish between "what is" and "what could be." Regarding leadership styles in particular, it's important to note that the managers' perceptions inform the answers, It would be appropriate to contrast this data with the leaders' assessments of their abilities and traits.

Given the limitations on how leadership style is perceived, it is recommended that future research explore styles from the perspective of leaders to gain a clearer understanding of the dynamic between leaders and followers. Furthermore, given that the study is quantitative, it is advised to employ additional methods of data collection to enhance the research. Additionally, qualitative research can aid in improving knowledge and comprehension of the concepts covered in this study. In light of the research findings, it is thought that it would be worthwhile to include additional constructs or substitutes in studies of a similar nature. As an illustration, competencies, organizational environment, and culture, among other topics related to the individual's relationship with his/her work environment.

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